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SECOND VICTIM PHENOMENON: THE PERIOPERATIVE PROVIDER PERSPECTIVE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Medical errors, adverse events (AE) and perioperative catastrophes have the potential to harm the patient and the healthcare professional (HCP). In these situations, there is a victim and second victim (SV). The first victim is the patient and the SV is the HCP. When an AE occurs, both victims are traumatized and require support. The literature revealed that the SV is overlooked and not sought out for support. When an SV is not supported, they are left feeling alone and overwhelmed with physical and psychological stress. The stress can put the HCP at risk of dropping out of their profession, or just surviving in their profession. Neither of these outcomes are beneficial for the wellbeing of the HCP or HCO. The goal after an AE is to provide supportive interventions so the HCP can thrive in their profession. A needs assessment was conducted to help determine if HCPs had adequate support or if they needed additional support after AEs. This project used the Second Victim Experience Support Tool (SVEST) to measure the second victims experience in relation to organizational support resources. Eighteen perioperative providers completed the SVEST survey. The results showed that nearly 50% of the participants were negatively affected by AE and desired immediate supportive interventions. The results indicated that poor support was associated with less self-efficacy and greater intention to turnover. The immediate supportive interventions desired were an opportunity to take time away from the unit (to a specific peaceful location to recover) or a confidential discussion with a peer to promote recovery after an AE.

Keywords: adverse event, healthcare organization, healthcare professional, second victim, second victim experience, Second Victim Experience Tool

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Background

The American Association of Nurse Anesthetists (AANA) has indicated that up to 67% of certified registered nurse anesthetists (CRNA) have been involved in a perioperative catastrophic event (van Pelt et al., 2019). Perioperative catastrophes are considered adverse events (AE) or events that cause harm to the patient, such as “death, cardiac arrest, myocardial infarction and intraoperative awareness” (van Pelt et al., 2019, p. 442). These events have undesirable effects on both the patient and the CRNA (van Pelt et al., 2019). In these types of events, the patient is recognized as a victim, as they are the casualty of the AE. However, there is often no consideration given to the CRNAs who were involved in or caused the AE to occur. In these situations, the CRNA can be identified as a victim. Generally speaking, the literature identifies the healthcare professional (HCP) who experiences an unpleasant emotional reaction that causes distress after an AE as a second victim (SV; Wijaya et al., 2018).

Wu (2000), a physician, introduced the phrase “second victim” 20 years ago. The patient is the first victim, and the physician is the SV (Wu, 2000). Wu noted that both the HCP and the patient agonize over the same medical mistake. According to Wu, SVs are not provided support after a medical error because the focus of the care is on the patient. Organizations do not identify a need to provide support to the SV (Wu, 2000). However, the SV should be provided support because they may be experiencing psychological distress from a medical error they may have caused.

Over the years, the phrase “second victim” has been defined in different ways. Denham (2007) defines SV as an HCP who suffers negative psychological effects due to harm caused to a patient. Patient harm has been associated with unintentional events or organizational system failures (Denham, 2007). Lewis, Baernholdt, and Hamric (2013) identified SV as a response to a medical error that causes the HCP to express feelings of anxiety and guilt. Edrees, Morlock, and

Wu (2017) define SV as an HCP who suffers an emotionally traumatic experience due to AEs. Scott et al. (2009) identified SV as an experience or phenomenon caused by a critical incident or unexpected event. Scott and colleagues determined that HCPs need to understand the emotional response of the SV to mitigate the SV phenomenon (SVP). Understanding the SV's emotional response allows the HCP to intervene and offer support when needed (Scott, 2019). Medical errors, unexpected events, and perioperative catastrophes can compromise patient care when HCPs are overwhelmed with emotional distress and have no emotional support.

Overcoming emotional distress depends on the SV's resilience (Tunajek, 2010). Resilience has been defined as the individual's internal emotional protective factors that assist them in handling challenging life events (Delgado, Upton, Ranse, Trentham, & Foster, 2017). Also, resilience promotes the balance of emotional, physical, and spiritual health (Tunajek, 2010). When an SV is affected by AEs, their resiliency is determined by maintaining a positive attitude, spirituality, coping skills, self-confidence, acknowledging limitations, and ability to learn from a situation (Tunajek, 2010). Coping after AEs is difficult, but support and a safe, reliable environment that promotes a positive patient safety culture have proven to enhance the ability to cope after AEs, thus increasing the HCP's resiliency (Edrees & Wu, 2017).

Significance

A national survey by the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) indicated that anesthesiologists feel responsible after a catastrophic event regardless of whether it was preventable (Gazoni, Amato, Malik, & Durieux, 2012). These events leave the anesthesiologist feeling depressed, anxious, and guilty (Gazoni et al., 2012). The ASA survey results indicated that 60% of respondents felt their quality of care was put at risk following a catastrophic event (Gazoni et al., 2012). However, regardless of whether the AE was preventable, more than 70% of the respondents believed that talking with a peer would be helpful (Gazoni et al., 2012).

The AANA conducted a survey regarding the aftermath of perioperative catastrophes among CRNAs (van Pelt et al., 2019). The respondents' emotions and care following a perioperative catastrophe mimicked those found by the ASA (Gazoni et al., 2012; van Pelt et al., 2019). Healthcare organizations have external programs such as an employee assistance program (EAP) to assist HCPs with an AE (van Pelt et al., 2019). There has been no evidence of whether the supportive interventions that an EAP offers are effective in decreasing an HCP's stress after a perioperative catastrophe (van Pelt et al., 2019). Second victim data would be helpful because the negative impact of a perioperative catastrophe has been associated with compromised patient care and with the HCPs leaving their profession (Scott & Mc Coig, 2016; van Pelt et al., 2019).

Annually, 98,000 people have died due to medical errors, which costs up to 29 billion dollars (Kohn, Corrigan, & Donaldson, 2000). The National Academy of Medicine reported that medical errors are on the rise and a leading cause of death in the United States (van Pelt et al., 2019). Since 1999, the Institute of Medicine has recommended that healthcare organizations (HCOs) create practices to improve patient safety culture.

A quasi-experimental study indicated an SV support program has a positive impact on patient safety culture (Wijaya et al., 2018). The authors implemented an SV support program at Bali International Medical Centre for 87 HCPs. A control group consisted of 103 HCPs who did not receive the support program (Wijaya et al., 2018). The program was adapted from a revision of a medically induced trauma support system (MITSS): The 2010 For You Tool Kit (Wijaya et al., 2018). Awareness, education, and implementation of the program were initiated and followed over a two-year period (Wijaya et al., 2018). The results showed the program had a positive effect on patient safety culture and is a necessary step to heal the SV (Wijaya et al., 2018).

Fiscally, an organization should seek to support their SVs since they are at high risk for burnout and dropping out of the profession (Del Grosso & Boyd, 2019). The consequences of

these risks lead to HCOs paying for overtime or replacing a CRNA (Mahoney, Lea, Schumann, & Jillson, 2020). Replacing an experienced CRNA costs an organization between \$145,000 and \$157,000 (Mahoney et al., 2020).

Support from the HCO is necessary to assist SVs in healing after AEs (Marmon & Heiss, 2015). Recovering after an event promotes healing, decreases stress, and prevents the SV from leaving their profession (Marmon & Heiss, 2015). In addition, HCO support has been found to have a positive effect on patient safety culture (Burlison et al, 2016). Unsupportive surgical cultures present a barrier for SVs to discuss surgical errors (Han et al., 2017). Second victims who feel blamed or shamed by their colleagues after an AE have trouble coping (Han et al., 2017). Forums such as morbidity and mortality conferences that provide a platform in which HCPs can learn from the AE can be accusatory and make the SV feel like a defendant (Han et al., 2017). Healthcare organizations that promote a just culture for HCPs mitigate shame and blame when AEs occur (Burlison et al., 2016).

Healthcare professionals and anesthesia providers need to focus on managing their well-being after AEs. Research has indicated that anesthesia providers do not generally reach out to receive support after AEs (Gazoni et al., 2012). Lack of support places the HCP at risk of developing psychological distress (Gazoni et al., 2012). Providing HCPs with appropriate interventions, access, and guidance can mitigate stress and improve resiliency among SVs. Given the significance of HCPs' feelings, increasing reports of medical errors or AEs, fiscal costs, and need for support, it is essential that quality improvement projects are conducted to understand the magnitude of the HCPs' experience, their responses, and of the resources they need to cope with the event. Their perceptions of these events and support services are needed to build a plan following AEs.

Problem Statement

At a local tertiary medical center in Southern California, physicians have a crisis management plan in place called Support 4 U Second Victim (S4USV) program to support physicians after AEs. This form of organized support is rare (Conway et al, 2011; Denham, 2007; Mira et al., 2015). Unfortunately, this form of support is not available for all HCPs. Healthcare organization leaders whose mission is to improve members' health should have programs that include all HCPs. Differences in organizational supportive resources after AEs make it challenging for all HCPs to improve their well-being.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice project was to develop a set of recommendations through which perioperative team members can receive support following AEs. The aims of this project are to assess current resources available to the perioperative team at the time of an AE, assess perioperative teams' experience with AEs, and provide the project facility recommendations based on the perioperative team needs for support after AEs.

The type of support received after the event is essential to the HCP's recovery (El Hechi et al., 2019; Seys et al., 2012). HCO's leaders' failure to provide adequate support for their members after AEs puts the organization at risk for negative events (Bleazard, 2019).

Supporting Framework

The conceptual framework used to guide this evidence-based project was the Iowa Model. The Iowa Model provided a framework for planning the essential steps to implement the project. A team of nurses from the University of Iowa hospitals, clinics, and college of nursing developed the Iowa Model in 1994 to help HCOs evaluate their evidence-based practices and determine their effectiveness (Titler et al., 2001). It was revised in June 2015, to make it easier to implement evidence-based practice changes in healthcare settings (Iowa Model Collaborative,

2017). Figure 1 presents the model, which has been extensively used worldwide and in all 50 states and consists of a seven-step process designed to improve clinical practices (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). This model has been useful in guiding nurses to use research to improve patient care (Titler et al., 2001). Details of the model application to the problem under study are outlined in the steps below.

Identifying Triggering Issues and Opportunities

The Iowa Model begins with identifying issues or opportunities that need improvement (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The focus of this project was to address the inequity of support resources available to perioperative team members who suffer from SVP. This inequity is significant for the perioperative team because the operating room is a high-risk environment where AEs occur frequently (Sonod et al., 2018). As previously stated, the project facility developed an S4USV peer support program for physicians but excluded HCPs such as nurses and nurse anesthetists. This exclusion is the triggering issue because all HCPs, according to the literature, would benefit from peer support after AEs. Healthcare organization leaders who provide support for SVs have a positive impact on patient care and HCPs' well-being (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017). Adequate support after AEs allows providers to improve their emotional well-being because many have reported being overwhelmed by stress (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017). Evidence-based practices for SV that promote well-being should be available to all providers to improve recovery after AEs.

State the Purpose

The second step of the Iowa Model is to state the purpose of the project. The purpose of this prospective project was to develop recommendations for how perioperative team members can receive support following AEs. This purpose was triggered due to the support offered to

physicians after AEs at the current HCO, which was documented as a best practice in the literature.

Form a Team

The third step is forming a team (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). For this project, the team conducted a strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and results (SOAR) analysis with stakeholders to identify resources that are beneficial to mitigating stress. The team worked collaboratively on the project to suggest a solution to mitigate stress following AEs. The team consisted of key stakeholders who were engaged and believed the clinical practice change was worthwhile (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Team members included managers from the perioperative arena, nurses, EAP staff, chief and assistant chief of anesthesiology, and unit-based team members. The team assisted in planning, guiding, and evaluating the project (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize Evidence

The fourth step of the Iowa Model involves reviewing and evaluating the evidence (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The electronic databases searched were be CINHALL, PubMed, OVID, and OneSearch. Also, professional organization websites such as that of the AANA were electronically accessed and searched. After the search was completed, the literature was placed in order of topic related ideas (Cullen et al., 2018). Synthesis of the research involved reviewing published literature and appraising the level of evidence to determine best clinical practices (Cullen et al., 2018). Strategies such as checklists and charts were useful in this step to assist with evaluating the evidence (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

Pilot the Practice Change

The fifth step is piloting the practice change. This was a multistep process that involved engaging HCPs, preparation, creation of an evaluation plan, collecting data, and providing

education (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The organization's resources needed to be considered in this stage, and a plan needed to be devised to prepare and guide HCPs for change (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The evidence captured through an analysis of the results was discussed with management. Recommendations that could be integrated into practice were provided to the leadership team in an executive summary.

Integrate and Sustain the Practice Change

The sixth step of the Iowa Model is the most difficult (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The workflow after a perioperative catastrophe needed to be addressed to create a plan for perioperative team members to receive assistance when AEs occur. The findings of this project revealed the perioperative team members' preferred method of support to mitigate the emotional response after AEs. The ultimate goal of the project was for the perioperative team to voice their preference for support resources to the leadership team.

Disseminate Results

The final step is to disseminate the results internally at the organization and externally through abstracts and journals (Cullen et al., 2018). Disseminating the results ensures the results are communicated so that recommendations can be provided to affect future practice (Polit & Beck, 2010). Internal dissemination is sharing the results with the organization through quality improvement teams (Cullen et al., 2018). At the project facility, results were shared with the unit-based team members who represent all classes of HCPs working in different units of the hospital. External dissemination includes sharing with other HCOs through presentations or publications (Cullen et al., 2018).

Nurses' ability to make changes in health care begins with identifying practices that need changing and understanding the perioperative team members' preferences regarding support after AEs. Once the preferred support strategies were identified, they were discussed with

management to provide recommendations for implementing support plans in the perioperative arena. The goal of the project was to utilize the Iowa Model to implement practices or processes to improve support and enhance an HCP's recovery after AEs.

Review of Literature

The literature review provides an overview of the relevant research related to the topic of SVP found through a search of relevant databases: CINAHL, EBSCO, PubMed, Ovid, and OneSearch. A combination of search terms was used, “second victim (SV),” “second victim experience (SVE),” “second victim phenomenon,” “second victims and CRNAs,” “errors and AEs in healthcare and CRNAs,” and “errors and AEs in healthcare.” The search was limited to articles written in English published or unpublished worldwide over the last 20 years. Also searched were national and state websites such as those of the AANA, ASA, Anesthesia Patient Safety Foundation, Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI), The Joint Commission, and MITSS.

Synthesis of Literature

The synthesis of the literature on SV research pertained to understanding the prevalence, experience, effects, desired support, and available strategies. Although the initial search was limited in the area of SV and CRNAs, more studies were found in medical and nursing literature. Therefore, the search was extended to nursing and medicine. The literature review synthesized current evidence on SVs and the need to provide support and guidance to perioperative team members who suffer as the SV.

Second Victim Phenomenon

Wu (2000) described SV as an unfortunate HCP’s unpleasant experience resulting from a medical error. It is described as unfortunate because the HCP lacked judgement, or their judgement caused the error, proving that HCPs make mistakes because they are human (Wu, 2000). In 2007, Denham added to the definition by including the psychological impact caused by the event. Denham (2007) believed any type of AE could have an emotional impact on the SV, not just medical error, and a plan is needed for the SV when an incident occurs. Healthcare

organizations must provide guidance following AEs to address the causes of the medical error and to support the emotionally injured HCP. Scott et al. (2009) agreed on a definition of SV to include “healthcare providers who are involved in an unanticipated adverse patient event, in a medical error and/or a patient-related injury and become victimized in the sense that the provider was traumatized by the event” (p. 326). Despite changes in the definition of SV, the implication is that HCPs are affected by medical error or injury caused to a patient (Denham, 2007; Scott et al., 2009; Scott et al., 2010; Wu, 2000). The AE has physiological and psychological consequences for the HCP that need to be addressed (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Gazoni et al., 2012; Han et al., 2017; Seys et al., 2012; van Pelt et al., 2019).

Incidence of Adverse Events

Helo and Moulton (2017) estimated that 1 in 10 hospital patients will experience AEs during their stay. Other literature has estimated that between 400,000 and 600,000 deaths occur annually related to medical errors (Helo & Moulton, 2017; Marmon & Heiss, 2015). Overall, HCPs will suffer from AEs or critical incidents at least once during their professional careers (Chung et al., 2018; Stone et al, 2017). Mira et al. (2015) indicated that one in three HCPs will be involved in AEs. These results are estimations but indicate that, over HCPs' careers, they will be exposed to AEs.

Impact of Adverse Events on Healthcare Professionals

The impact of SVP on HCPs causes them to suffer negative physiological and psychological consequences such as stress, anxiety, guilt, and anger (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Chung et al., 2018; Gazoni et al., 2012; Han et al., 2017; Seys et al., 2012; van Pelt et al., 2019). Other research indicates that an SV feels sad and embarrassed after an AE (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Gazoni et al., 2012; Han et al., 2017; Seys et al., 2012; van Pelt et al., 2019). These emotions are sometimes compared to those experienced by individuals with post-traumatic stress

disorder (Burlison et al., 2016; Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017). The physiological consequences most commonly reported are rapid heart rate, inability to sleep, nausea, and decreased appetite (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Mohamadi-Bolabanabad et al., 2019). The negative consequences are overwhelming for the SV and may lead to substance abuse, intention to leave, burnout, or suicide (Scott et al., 2009).

Scott and colleagues (2009) conducted a qualitative study that identified six stages of emotions SVs experience after AEs. These stages identify a pathway for recovery, which helps to identify strategies that can be used at specific points to intervene and provide support. Healthcare organization leaders can use this information to develop strategies to mitigate stress. The six stages of the SVP are chaos and accident response; intrusive reflection; restoring personal integrity; enduring the inquisition; obtaining emotional first aid; and moving on, dropping out or surviving (Scott et al., 2009, p. 325).

Psychological and Professional Impact

The psychological consequences experienced during each stage will be described in addition to the potential outcomes if the response to an AE is not supported by an intervention. Healthcare organization leaders must be cognizant that the severity of the SV response is influenced by the level of harm caused to the patient, judgement by colleagues, and consequences from the organization or state (Gazoni et al., 2012). The stages proposed by Scott and colleagues are as follows.

The first stage is the SV's response to the AE, which is the feeling of chaos (Scott et al., 2009). This is the commotion the HCP feels after the AE (Scott et al., 2009). In this stage, HCPs report problems focusing (Scott et al., 2009). This stage coincides with feelings of guilt due to the SV's attempts to learn what caused the AE and the role they played in it (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Gazoni et al., 2012; Han et al., 2017; Seys et al., 2012; Ullström et al., 2014; van Pelt et

al., 2019). During Stage One, the focus of care is on the patient, as they may be in crisis and need assistance (Scott et al., 2009). The SV's colleagues need to be aware that the SV may have difficulty focusing on the task at hand, and colleagues may need to take over to manage the patient crisis (Helo & Moulton, 2017; Scott et al., 2009).

In Stage Two, the HCP re-examines the situation to understand what happened to cause the AE. During this stage, the SVs begin to doubt their professional skills (Scott et al., 2009). The SV may also show another common emotion at this stage, self-doubt (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Scott et al., 2009).

In Stage Three, the HCP seeks guidance from a trusted peer to ensure their feelings are recognized as reasonable (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Helo & Moulton, 2017; Scott et al., 2009). Although there may be different support resources available, SVs prefer support from their peers (Han et al., 2017; Merandi et al., 2018). This stage can linger depending on the level of harm caused to the patient and the type of support the SV received. (Scott et al., 2009). The SV may not be able to move beyond Stage Three without support (Scott et al., 2009). In this stage of recovery, the SV is influenced by the culture of the department and colleagues' support (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Scott et al., 2009). A supportive environment assists in disclosing the incident and in restoring the SV's confidence and integrity (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Scott et al., 2009).

In Stage Four, the HCP faces repercussions, such as internal review by the organization, legal consequences, or licensure revocation (Scott et al., 2009). Han et al. (2017) indicated that 50% of HCPs do not want to disclose their error due to fear of litigation. Although the duty of disclosure is not easy, it allows the SV to acknowledge the AE and communicate with the patient regarding who, what, when, and how the AE occurred (Helo & Moulton, 2017). It is important to understand the disclosure process at the organization to determine what needs to be completed and how disclosure will be accomplished (Scott et al., 2009).

Stage Five is when the SV seeks guidance, peer support, or professional support if needed (Scott et al., 2009). Peer support can ease emotional distress about 60% of the time (Scott et al., 2010). A peer supporter is a colleague who listens to the SV without judgement and empathizes with his/her feelings (Ullström et al., 2014). Helo and Moulton (2017) indicated it is easier for some HCPs to discuss the AE than it is to discuss their feelings. This may be due to their reluctance to admit wrongdoing, which can lead to feelings of shame (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017)

In Stage Six, the SVs determine if they are going to survive, thrive, or drop out of their profession, as the AE can damage professional and personal lives (Scott et al., 2009; van Pelt et al., 2019; Wijaya et al., 2018). For example, van Pelt et al. (2019) indicated that CRNAs with fewer than 10 years of experience had a greater experience of stress after an AE and had a hard time accepting responsibility for it. These results indicated that experienced CRNAs coped better after an AE (van Pelt et al., 2019). Nineteen percent of SVs indicated that they never fully recovered, and there was no difference in the experience between males and females (van Pelt et al., 2019). It is important that HCO leaders understand the SV experience to develop a plan for intervention and guidance (Denham, 2007; Scott et al., 2009). This plan may help prevent negative coping skills such as substance abuse, leaving the profession, burnout, and suicide.

Risk of Substance Abuse after an Adverse Event

The risk of substance abuse is high after an AE (Wu, 2000). Healthcare professionals turn to substance abuse because they have no means of reducing or coping with stress (Helo & Moulton, 2017; Wu, 2000). A cross-sectional study of 5,788 nurses and physicians found that HCPs were 1.6 times more likely to abuse medications after AEs if support was not provided (Van Gerven et al., 2016).

Intention to Leave After an Adverse Event

Nurses who experience AEs are more likely to leave their profession (Chiang, & Chang, 2012). This is a problem because of the current nursing shortage (Sharififard et al., 2019). Nurses will decide to leave their profession when they are overwhelmed with stress and do not receive support resources (Chiang, & Chang, 2012; Sharififard et al., 2019). However, when supported by managers and colleagues, nurses may elect not to leave the profession due to feeling valued and listened to during times of stress (Chiang, & Chang, 2012). A cross-sectional study was conducted among 206 nurses regarding their intention to leave (Sharififard et al., 2019). The study found that the majority of nurses had the intention to leave their workplace if they were not supported by their organization (Sharififard et al., 2019). Therefore, support benefitted the nurse and the organization because it decreased stress and the risk of leaving the organization (Sharififard et al., 2019).

A cross-sectional study was conducted to uncover nurses' perceptions regarding their HCOs' patient safety culture and medical errors (Hwang & Park, 2014). Researchers surveyed nurses at 33 Korean public hospitals using the Hospital Ethical Climate Survey (Hwang & Park, 2014). The study found that a supportive culture or climate can have a positive effect on nurses' intention to leave (Hwang & Park, 2014). The results were that a medical error did not put nurses at risk for leaving the organization because the errors were viewed as opportunities for constructive knowledge exchange, which made nurses feel supported (Hwang & Park, 2014).

Burnout

Burnout has been defined as a psychological syndrome that can cause HCPs to feel emotionally depleted and detached from reality as well as lower their sense of self-worth (Stehman et al., 2019). Healthcare professionals with untreated trauma may suffer from chronic stress leading to the psychological state of burnout (Garcia et al., 2019; Sanfilippo et al., 2018).

A national survey conducted among anesthesia providers on burnout indicated that 50% of responding anesthesiologists suffer from burnout, and stressful work environments increase the incidence of burnout (Sanfilippo et al., 2018; Shanafelt et al., 2009). Anesthesiologists who work in cardiac care are exposed to life-threatening patient scenarios daily (Sanfilippo et al., 2018). Thus, adding AEs to an already stressful work environment increases the risk of burnout (Garcia et al., 2019; Sanfilippo et al., 2018; Shanafelt et al., 2009). Research indicates that support decreases the incidence of burnout among this population (Sanfilippo et al., 2018).

A systematic review and meta-analysis were conducted regarding the influence of burnout on patient safety (Garcia et al., 2019). The analysis indicated that HCPs who suffer from burnout could negatively influence patient safety (Garcia et al., 2019; Shanafelt et al., 2009). The review indicated a support program should include several factors to decrease burnout and foster collegial and management support and teamwork (Garcia et al., 2019).

Suicide

National studies have indicated that physician and nurse suicide rates are higher than those of the general population (Davidson et al., 2019; Gold et al., 2013; Stehman et al., 2019). Suicide is defined as taking one's life, whether purposely or not (Yentis et al., 2019). Healthcare providers' risk of suicide is increased when there is stress on the job and lack of support (Gold et al., 2013; Milner et al., 2016; Scott, 2019). In general, when HCPs suffer from stress, they do not seek support because they fear disclosure and being labeled as having psychological problems (Stehman et al., 2019). Lack of support leads to developing unhealthy coping skills that increase the risk of suicide (Stehman et al., 2019). The field of anesthesia has been identified as at high risk for suicide due to providers' exposure to critical incidents and increased access to drugs (Scott, 2019; Yentis et al., 2019).

Benefits of Organizational Support

Cabilan and Kynoch (2017) reviewed the literature on nurses as SVs. The findings indicated that nurses' stress response after AEs is increased, and the type of support received affects the stress response (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017). Nurses were more willing to disclose their medical errors when they are supported by their managers (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017). However, it was determined that HCPs do not receive support from their HCOs 68% of the time (Scott et al., 2009). Relieving stress and providing support for HCP affect both the patient and the organization positively.

It is necessary for HCOs to have a plan to provide support for SVs (Denham, 2007; Wu, 2000). Research has found SVs feel supported and not alone when they can talk to someone after a medical error (Denham, 2007; Wu, 2000). The well-being of the HCP is positively correlated with the patient's well-being (Shanafelt et al., 2009). It is important that HCOs implement strategies to reduce HCPs' stress and promote their well-being (Shanafelt et al., 2009).

Identification of Second Victim Based on Prevalence of Adverse Events

Healthcare organization leaders can begin to identify SVs by assessing the number of AEs that occur on the unit or within the facilities. Obtaining a count of AEs will assist in developing an intervention and support plan. Surveying HCPs regarding their need for support also assists in developing appropriate interventions to decrease feelings of traumatization (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Coughlan et al., 2017; Miller et al., 2019; Ullström et al., 2014).

A qualitative study indicated that HCOs need to identify incidents of AEs to determine the prevalence of SVs (Scott et al., 2009). This study was accomplished by asking HCPs questions regarding the previous 12 months of their working career (Scott et al., 2009). The first question was whether they experienced AEs that affected their professional performance (Scott et al., 2009). The second question was whether they received support (Scott et al., 2009). The

answers enabled HCO leaders to identify SVs through their analysis of the prevalence of AEs (Scott et al., 2009). This method is useful when an organization has not been collecting data regarding HCPs' negative experiences with AEs and has not determined the number of HCPs needing support. Once the prevalence of SVs is identified, then prevention and treatment plans can be developed to assist with emotional trauma (Scott et al., 2009).

The SVEST has been used to assess the experience and available support resources provided by HCOs following AEs (Burlison et al., 2017). The SVEST is a valid psychometric evaluation tool that assesses the physiological and psychological symptoms associated with being an SV (Burlison et al., 2017). This tool can be used to evaluate current resources and those needed for SVs.

Best Practices to Combat Second Victim

Denham (2007) recognized that HCOs were neglecting to care for HCPs who experienced AEs. Denham claimed that SVs were left to suffer alone because there was no assistance plan. Thus, Denham proposed rights for caregivers known as Five Rights for SV (FRSV) to provide them fair treatment after AEs (Denham, 2007). Denham's FRSV were represented by the acronym TRUST, with each letter representing a process of care:

T stands for treatment that is non-punitive, which allows the SV to come forward and discuss what happened and the organization to make improvements to ensure the AE does not occur again

R stands for the respect with which HCOs need to treat the SV

U represents offering understanding to the SV, meaning the HCP's feelings are appreciated, and they are allowed to grieve, which improves their recovery

S stands for support

T refers to transparency to create opportunities for learning (Denham, 2007).

Often, the HCP who made a mistake can contribute feedback to prevent others from making that mistake (Denham, 2007). It was projected that HCOs that adopted the FRSV decreased medical errors (Denham, 2007). The FRSV have not been mentioned as a pathway or a framework, but they provide a guideline.

In 2010, the IHI indicated that HCOs leadership has failed SV because HCOs leadership were unaware of the prevalence of AEs (Conway et al., 2011). Awareness of the prevalence of AEs helps HCOs leadership understand the magnitude of the problem so that events can be effectively addressed. The goal of the IHI was to provide a crisis plan to support the patient, family, and healthcare team (Conway et al., 2011). The IHI found that only 30% of 50 HCOs had a crisis plan in place despite these plans' ensuring fair and just treatment for SVs (Conway et al., 2011).

In 2018, The Joint Commission (TJC, 2018) provided recommendations for HCOs leadership on how to support SVs. According to TJC, almost 50% of all HCPs will be SVs at some point in their careers, with the majority never seeking help unless directly contacted to do so. TJC's goal for SV care was to provide support to prevent the reoccurrence of errors, as there are negative effects on the SV that can later increase the chances of errors and lower the quality of patient care (TJC, 2018).

For the past 20 years, many HCOs have failed to provide the support that SVs require. However, there have been national, state, and other recommendations for them to do so. The continued lack of support, despite recommendations, leaves HCPs shouldering the negative emotional consequences of a medical error (Ross, 2018).

Second Victim Peer Support Programs

There are several programs designed to support SVs, but they are not widely or consistently implemented. Peer support programs have been documented to be the most effective

method for addressing SV needs (Hu et al., 2012). Several studies have indicated that SVs prefer support from their colleagues, as colleagues offer reassurance that they are not alone (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; El Hechi et al., 2019). Peer supporters are respected colleagues in whom SVs feel comfortable confiding (El Hechi et al., 2019). Some HCOs have trained peer supporters to respond to SV needs (Wu et al., 2020). Educational training programs include instruction in role playing, listening, empathizing, and, if needed, developing a plan for continued support (El Hechi et al., 2019). There are various types of peer support programs available to assist with SV well-being.

One program, called Critical Incident Stress Management (CISM), was designed for first responders to cope with symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (Stone et al., 2017). A critical incident is an event that affects both the first victim and the second victim physically and or psychologically and which has the potential to cause harm or actually causes harm (Stone et al., 2017). According to Stone et al. (2017), the signs and symptoms an individual suffers after a critical incident are anxiety, lack of confidence, and difficulty focusing on tasks. The CISM provides on-scene support to all affected by the critical incident (Stone et al., 2017). Stone et al. (2017) set out to modify the CISM program for 57 CRNAs at a Level One trauma facility. The CRNA CISM program provided electronic education regarding critical incidents, a guideline to follow after an incident, and supportive guidance to allow for the expression of feelings (Stone et al., 2017). Over half of the CRNAs felt the program was successful and provided supportive guidance as necessary (Stone et al., 2017). Guidance after an event was key because a common complaint among SVs was the lack of awareness of available support services (Hu et al., 2012)

The Clinician Peer Support Program (PSP) was developed at a large tertiary hospital to support physicians, physician assistants, residents, nurse practitioners, and CRNAs who suffered emotional distress from AEs (Lane et al., 2018). The goal of the PSP was to train HCPs to

provide peer support and to enhance the HCP's well-being after AEs by utilizing the HCO's resources (Lane et al., 2018). The peer supporters allowed SVs to express their thoughts and concerns (Lane et al., 2018). The support process begins with a referral from risk management to the peer supporter who contacts the SV (Lane et al., 2018). The peer supporter can refer the SV to a higher level of support if needed (Lane et al., 2018). The advantage of the PSP was that it complemented the EAP by providing immediate in-hospital support and provided a referral to EAP if needed (Lane et al., 2018). The disadvantage of the PSP was that SVs were referred through risk management, which meant that not all cases of SV were captured, as HCP may not have reported them (Lane et al., 2018).

Johns Hopkins Hospital established the Resilience in Stressful Events (RISE) Program in 2010 to improve SV guidance and provide prompt assistance (Edrees et al., 2016). The hospital planned to pilot RISE in the pediatric department before launching it hospital-wide (Edrees et al., 2016). The goal of RISE was to improve the SV's well-being, collegial support, and resilience (Edrees et al., 2016). Once AEs occurred, the peer supporter responded within 30 minutes and met with the SV within 12 hours (Edrees et al., 2016). There were two peer supporters on call 24 hours a day, and AEs were reported by any HCP (Edrees et al., 2016). In the first year, there was approximately one call per month, which progressively increased to three calls per month by year three (Edrees et al., 2016). According to Edrees et al. (2016), 45% of the calls were related to a patient's death, and 21% were related to an AE. Other calls were related to difficult situations the HCP experienced, such as assault, burnout, and conflicts with their peers (Edrees et al., 2016).

The forYou Program was guided by Jean Watson's theoretical framework of transpersonal caring and the CISM (Hirschinger et al., 2015). The University of Missouri Health Care launched the program over a five-year period with 6,500 employees (Hirschinger et al.,

2015). The goal of the program was to provide immediate emotional aid and increase awareness of the signs and symptoms of SV to mitigate distress so that the HCPs would succeed in their careers (Hirschinger et al., 2015). This model has three tiers of support for SVs and guidance for peer supporters (Hirschinger et al., 2015). The first tier is colleague and supervisor support (Hirschinger et al., 2015). The second tier is trained peer colleague support, which includes face-to-face or group debriefings (Hirschinger et al., 2015). The third tier is organizational guidance, such as counseling (Hirschinger et al., 2015). Over a five-year period, there were 1,075 support services offered, and 971 of the cases did not require an outside referral for support (Hirschinger et al., 2015). Hirschinger et al. (2015) found that most HCPs do not actively seek support because they do not feel they are suffering (Hirschinger et al., 2015). The study concluded that having a SV plan was key to decreasing HCPs' suffering after AEs (Hirschinger et al., 2015).

Many factors contribute to SV recovery. Healthcare professionals often feel isolated after AEs, yet they are unwilling to obtain assistance (Cabilan & Kynoch, 2017; Lane et al., 2018; Ullström et al., 2014). Healthcare professionals are trained to take care of the patient but fall short when it comes to taking care of themselves and their colleagues. Ultimately, without support after AEs, the HCP's job satisfaction and quality of life decrease (Lane et al., 2018; Miller et al., 2019). This may lead to an unhealthy professional lifestyle and place the HCP at high risk for burnout (Lane et al., 2018; Miller et al., 2019). Second victim programs have been proven to assist with coping. However, despite the multitude of SV recommendations and array of programs available, 68% of SVs still do not receive support (Scott et al., 2009).

Methods

The purpose of this DNP was to develop a set of recommendations for how perioperative team members receive support following AEs. The aims of this project were as follows:

- A. Assess current support resources available to the perioperative team at the time of AEs.
- B. Assess the perioperative teams' experience with AEs.
- C. Provide the project facility with recommendations based on the perioperative team's need for support after AEs.

The methods section includes a discussion of the project's setting, sample, design, SOAR analysis, procedures, measures, data analysis, and ethical considerations

Setting

The project took place specifically in the perioperative department at a Southern California tertiary medical center with 11 operating rooms. The perioperative department was an inpatient and outpatient facility that performs an average of 13,000 procedures per year. The patient population ranged from two years of age and older. The patient health status ranged from healthy to critically ill. The procedures at the hospital included obstetrics, gynecology, urology, vascular, general, oncology, and thoracic surgical cases.

Participants

The participants were members of the perioperative team who work in the project facility. Perioperative team members included registered nurses, surgical technicians, and CRNAs. Anesthesia technicians, physicians, surgeons, management, and environmental safety workers were excluded from the project to adhere to organization policies and procedures when employees conduct research or a quality improvement project at their place of employment. The perioperative staff members were informed of the project during their morning and evening huddles prior to the beginning of their shift (social distancing of six feet and personal protective

equipment were maintained due to COVID-19). A flyer was posted on the communication board to inform the perioperative staff of the project (Appendix H). They received an informational script that included a link to the Qualtrics survey used in the project via their work email (Appendix J).

Design

This evidence-based practice project used a prospective cross-sectional design. Information from the literature, best practices at the project facility, and the SVEST data and SOAR analysis were used to identify support resources available or needed to mitigate distress following an AE. The goal was to make recommendations to management and leadership on the immediate supportive interventions the perioperative team members needed following AEs based on the qualitative narratives obtained through the SOAR analysis and the quantitative data obtained from the SVEST data.

Focus Groups

Focus groups with key stakeholders such as peri-operative nurses, CRNAs, and surgical technicians were planned. The focus groups utilized the SOAR strategy for narrative data collection and analysis. The SOAR analysis is a strategic tool that guided the first steps of the project. This plan evaluates the HCO's resources' strengths, opportunities, aspirations, and results. The process of the SOAR analysis was focused on bringing the perioperative team members together to identify the strengths of resources available to them, the opportunities for a better work environment, the aspirations they hold and would like to see added to their work environment, and the results that will be provided as recommendations to the leadership team. This approach focuses on member engagement and the strengths of the organization through an appreciative inquiry approach (Starvos & Hinrichs, 2009).

There are four fundamental questions for a SOAR analysis (Starvos & Hinrichs, 2009). The first question is about identifying the organization's greatest strengths (Starvos & Hinrichs, 2009). The second question identifies the opportunities and what the participants desire (Starvos & Hinrichs, 2009). The third question identifies the participants' (staff and leaders) aspirations. The aspirations of the HCO's leaders are examined in the HCO mission, vision, and quality metrics. The mission of the HCO's leadership was to "provide high quality, affordable health care services and to improve the health of our members and the communities we serve" (Kaiser Permanente, 2019, para.1). The HCO's leadership vision is to be "trusted partners in total health, collaborating with the people to help them thrive, and creating communities that are among the healthiest in the nation" (Kaiser Permanente, 2019, para.8). The mission and vision of the project facilities' aspirations are focused on improving health and collaborating with members to help them thrive.

The final component in the SOAR analysis is the results. In this step, the group will determine, identify, and outline the resources needed to succeed. This final component of the analysis was addressed by determining measurable outcomes and the resources needed following AEs (Starvos & Hinrichs, 2009). The results are measurable and linked to specific, measurable, attainable, relevant time-based (SMART) goals determined by the group (Starvos & Hinrichs, 2009).

Procedures

The Iowa Model was intended to be used to guide the implementation of the project. However, the project facility's institutional review board (IRB) required modifications prior to implementation. Therefore, some of the steps of the model were omitted due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions. The initial step in the model identified the knowledge-focused trigger or opportunity to improve practice or outcomes (Cullen et al., 2018). In the project hospital, the

perioperative team did not have access to the same resources as other HCP's following AE. This was a problem because the perioperative team did not receive immediate support or guidance to assist them with recovery after AEs. The lack of immediate support and unequal resources following AE was the identified trigger because HCPs who experience an AE indicated they were in distress but were not offered immediate supportive interventions.

The second step of the Iowa Model was to state the purpose of the project. The purpose of the DNP project, as stated earlier, was to assess perioperative team members' knowledge of current resources and their perceptions of the resources available following AEs to develop recommendations for management and leadership. The recommendations will provide access to needed support resources for perioperative team members following AE.

The third step in the Iowa Model would have been the formation of a team to guide project implementation. Leadership, perioperative team members, and anesthesiologists were on board as a team. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the team could not gather and meet in person since doing so would have violated restrictions of social distancing. In addition, during the project's implementation, the facility was inundated with COVID-19 patients, and most staff members were deployed to other units.

Additionally, a SOAR analysis was not conducted in the way that it was originally planned due to social distancing requirements. The SOAR analysis would have allowed perioperative team members at the project facility to come together and discuss the processes in place for dealing with AEs and ways to improve these. The SOAR analysis did not take place at the project facility. Instead, it took place during a union Zoom meeting educational presentation for CRNAs. The project's author gave the educational presentation. The meeting's educational objectives for SVP in the perioperative setting were to discuss the meaning of SV, identify the

risks and stages of an SV, understand the professional consequences of the SV, identify current resources available for an SV, and identify desired resources for an SV.

After the meeting, CRNAs discussed for about 30 minutes the resources that were available that assisted in their well-being and the resources that were needed. Although the strategic plan for the SOAR analysis was modified, it provided a platform for CRNAs to come together, brainstorm, and collect qualitative data on the support needed after AEs. During the discussion the CRNAs realized there was unequal access to resources after an AE. The CRNAs felt that the equal access to needed resources could improve the health outcomes for CRNAs.

The qualitative data were collected through a SOAR analysis and quantitative data were gathered via the SVEST survey. Analysis of the group's feedback consisted of narrative themes regarding support resources available for SVs and those needed. Current organizational practices to improve the well-being of other CRNAs following AEs were explored. Also discussed were best practices that should be initiated following an AE, such as a policy or protocol to ensure that all members are treated equally and fairly after an AE.

The fourth step of the Iowa Model is to gather, assemble, and synthesize the evidence (Doody & Doody, 2011). This step was accomplished. A literature review was conducted, and articles were appraised to determine the strength of the evidence (Doody & Doody, 2011). After evaluating the evidence and its quality, it was determined in collaboration with the team leader that there was sufficient evidence to explore the need to provide immediate supportive interventions after an AE. There was additional evidence in the literature provided by the AANA and TJC that validated the benefits of addressing SV needs. TJC (2018) indicated that a proactive approach of immediate support after an AE offsets the negative domino effect of AEs. Proactively reaching out to support the HCP has a positive effect on their well-being, which, in turn, positively affects patient care.

The fifth step of the Iowa Model involved devising a plan for accomplishing the project, which included making recommendations for management regarding the resources desired by HCPs after AEs. This plan was partially implemented as follows. First, recruitment for the SOAR analysis was modified. Initially, perioperative team members were to be recruited. Due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions requiring social distancing, the format for the SOAR analysis changed. The SOAR analysis took place virtually with CRNA members who are a part of a Union in Southern California. The findings from the SOAR analysis helped collect qualitative data. The SOAR analysis provided a platform where members openly brainstormed ideas regarding their views for support following AEs. An informal discussion took place after the presentation and consisted of an open dialogue. Four open-ended questions were addressed:

- A. What are the perioperative teams' greatest resources provided following AEs?
- B. Are there gaps in the resources provided following AEs to perioperative team members?
- C. What resources would we like to see available to perioperative team members following AEs?
- D. What measures as a perioperative team can we take to make sure perioperative team members' needs are met following AEs?

Second, the SVEST was used to assess perioperative staff members' experiences and desire for support following AEs on the Qualtrics platform (Appendix C). The SVEST provided an assessment of the psychological and physical distress as well as satisfaction with the current support resources after an AE. Use of the SVEST provided an opportunity to improve practice outcomes for an SV and helped collect quantitative data.

A script was created and sent via email to inform the participants of the project. The script included a description of the aims and that participation was voluntary. The script also informed participants that the decision to participate would have no effect on their employment.

A link to the SVEST survey was provided in the email. Once the participants accessed the survey link, it took them to an informational sheet (Appendix H). The sheet was provided in lieu of a consent form as determined by the project facility's IRB. This document provided information regarding the project's purpose, duration, risks, benefits, and confidentiality. Since the project was deemed to pose minimal risk, informed consent was not required. After reading the informational sheet, if individuals chose to participate, they proceeded to the four multiple-choice demographics questions and 36 SVEST survey questions that used a five-point-Likert scale. The emails were sent to the perioperative team members' work emails. Perioperative team members were informed during huddles of the project at the beginning of their shift. There were two shifts, morning and evening. A flyer was placed on the communication board to advertise the project.

The sixth step of the Iowa Model is the discussion and recommendation developed from the SVEST data and SOAR analysis. The discussion and recommendation for the project were tabulated from the results of the SVEST and SOAR analysis.

The seventh step of the Iowa Model is to disseminate the information learned from the project. The SVEST data regarding providers' preferences for support will be shared with management, perioperative team members, and EAP. The dissemination will include providing a report of the findings to the department's administrative team and the research team at KP. The findings will also be presented to union representatives to discuss CRNAs' preferences after an AE. Additionally, findings will be presented at local KP institutions, a regional conference, other conferences, and possibly via publication.

Measures

Two measures were used for the quantitative portion of this project. The first was the demographics survey, which gathered information regarding the participants' personal characteristics, such as age, gender, professional title, and years of experience (Appendix C).

The second measure was the SVEST. This tool was validated using confirmatory factor analysis and internal consistency ratings. The Cronbach alpha score for the tool ranged from .6 to .89 (Burlison et al., 2017). The Cronbach alpha score indicated that the instrument was reliable (Polit & Beck, 2010). The SVEST has been used in other studies and has been determined to be a reliable and valid survey for the assessment of the SV experience (Burlison et al., 2017).

The SVEST contains 29 questions and two outcome variables utilizing two different five-point Likert scales for the two subscales within it (Burlison et al., 2017). The SVEST contains seven dimensions, distress psychological and physical, support from colleagues, supervisors, the organization, non-work-related, and professional self-efficacy (Burlison et al., 2017). The two outcome variables are turnover and absenteeism (Burlison et al., 2017).

The seven dimensions were measured in relation to AE experienced by the participants (Burlison et al., 2017). Their reactions were graded on a 5-point Likert scale where 1 was strongly disagree and 5 was strongly agree (Burlison et al., 2017). Assessment of the participants' desire for support was based on support from colleagues, supervisors, the organization, and non-work-related support. A five-point Likert scale was used with 1 meaning does not desire, and 5 meaning strongly desire (Burlison et al., 2017). The Qualtrics platform was used to deploy the survey and collect data. Approval for the use of the SVEST was granted by Dr. Scott who assisted in the creation of the survey (Appendix F).

The measure used for the qualitative portion of this project was the SOAR analysis. A narrative summary of the CRNA Zoom discussion group session was collected on lined paper.

The themes, patterns, and ideas were collected and identified for analysis. The SOAR analysis provided a platform to discuss opportunities and aspirations for changes to assist with CRNAs' and the perioperative team's recovery after an AE.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze age, gender, profession, and years of experience in the profession. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, means, Cronbach alpha, correlations, and *p* scores via Qualtrics, Excel spreadsheets, and SPSS 27. The SVEST had instructions for analysis of the survey (Appendix E). These instructions stated there are seven dimensions and two outcome variables (Burlison et al., 2017). The dimensions were identified as psychological, physical distress, colleague, supervisor, institutional and non-work-related support, and professional efficacy (Burlison et al., 2017). These dimensions were categorized with different survey questions and described in the scoring SVEST (Burlison et al., 2017). The two outcomes of turnover and absenteeism were also categorized. The survey scoring guide assisted with an accurate assessment of the dimensions and outcomes. This data allowed for recommendations to be made based on the perioperative teams' answers. The project author collaborated with the team leader, and the data were transferred to an Excel spreadsheet and SPSS 27. The team leader assisted the project author with a data plan.

Ethical Considerations

The project was submitted to the institutional review board at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) and at the project facility. Both organizations granted approval for the project's implementation. Management at the project facility provided a letter and granted permission to conduct the project with changes to implementation due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This was due to the risk of exposure to the virus for both the project author and the

participants. The IRB at CSUF approved the use of the Iowa Model as a framework and the SVEST survey (Appendix E). The project facility granted approval for the project to be implemented, with the exception that only portions of the IOWA Model could be executed. In addition, the project facility did not allow CRNAs at the project facility to participate since it was believed to be a conflict of interest for the project author (Appendix B and Appendix K). As a result, recruitment was focused on the preoperative team, and CRNAs were excluded.

The recruitment flyer, informational sheet, and use of Qualtrics to disseminate the SVEST survey were approved by both IRBs. The IRB at CSUF and the project facility were informed that all identifying information about the participants was confidential and anonymous. All identifying information was removed, and participants were only identified by the demographic data collected from the returned surveys. The data were kept on a password-protected computer stored in a locked office at the project facility. The data were also protected on the Qualtrics platform with the use of a password.

Analysis Plan for SVEST Data

The results were tabulated using the scoring instructions for the SVEST on Qualtrics (see Appendix D). The mean, standard deviation, Cronbach alpha, and percentages were computed for the seven dimensions and two outcomes. The data were transferred to tables for clarity of results for the seven dimensions and two outcomes. The higher the scores on the dimensions, per the scoring survey, indicate the participants recognized the support dimension as inadequate (Burlison et al., 2017). The SVEST was graded on a five-point Likert scale with 4 to 5 indicating desire and 1 to 2 indicating does not desire (Burlison et al., 2017). The table presents the percentage for support desired and not desired after an AE. The results are limited to the participants' agreement on the negative effects of the second victim experience (SVE; Burlison

et al., 2017). The results were tabulated with the assistance of the team lead and placed in the Qualtrics, Excel spreadsheet and SPSS 27.

Results

The purpose of the DNP project was to evaluate and identify the participants' support resources available and needed following an AE. The data gathered from the SVEST survey and SOAR analysis were tabulated, and recommendations were developed based on the responses. Adverse events have a negative effect on the patient and the HCPs. The assessment of the SVEST and SOAR analysis provided insight into the types of supportive interventions preferred by the HCPs after an AE.

Participant Characteristics

The sample consisted of 14 registered nurses and four surgical technicians who completed the online Qualtrics SVEST survey distributed from January 11, 2021, to February 21, 2021. As seen in Table 1, the demographic data included age, gender, professional title, and years of experience on the job. The demographic data were separated into three categories: demographics, descriptors, and number and percentage of participants in each category. All data were tabulated on Qualtrics, Excel spreadsheets, and SPSS 27. The demographic data in Table 1 indicate that 77.8% of the participants were registered nurses, 88.9% female, 44.4% had greater than 19 years of working experience in the perioperative department, and 33.3% were between the ages of 46 and 55, or older than 55. Only 22.2% of the participants were surgical technicians, 11.1% were aged 36 to 45, and 5.6% had fewer than five years of service in the perioperative department.

Table 1*Participant Demographics*

Demographic	Descriptor	N (%)
Age	26-35	4 (22.2)
	36-45	2 (11.1)
	46-55	6 (33.3)
	>55	6 (33.3)
Gender	Female	16 (88.9)
	Male	2 (11.1)
Professional Title	Registered Nurse	14 (77.8)
	Surgical Technician	4 (22.2)
Years of Experience	< 5 years	1 (5.6)
	5-10 years	2 (11.1)
	11-19 years	4 (22.2)
	20-29 years	8 (44.4)
	>30years	3 (16.7)

SOAR Analysis

The SOAR analysis was not conducted as planned due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The project author presented the project to CRNA union members from Southern California via Zoom. This platform gave CRNAs from different facilities an opportunity to share their ideas and perceptions on the topic and to educate members regarding the need for support after an AE. There were 50 CRNA members logged into the Zoom meeting.

Table 2*SOAR Analysis*

Strengths	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer support strong in some facilities • Union Peer support program • EAP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate with the S4USV Program so it can be available for CRNAs • Develop a policy to ensure all CRNAs are offered the same interventions
Aspirations	Results
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the well-being of CRNAs • Supportive interventions that need to take place post-event • A break after the event and ability to step out • Re assignment when errors occur 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 2021, review preoperative policies related to AEs with a focus on resources for the SV • By 2022, develop a policy on the process and procedures following an AE with a focus SV care • In 2022, collaborate with hospital administration and human resources to create a peer support program

After the meeting, the CRNAs discussed their organizations' strengths, aspirations and how supportive resources could be improved. Four questions were addressed and analysis of the responses is presented in Table 2. The first question was regarding the greatest resources provided to perioperative teams following AEs. Some individuals felt that the peer support at their facility was their greatest resource. Others preferred to use EAP if needed. Not all individuals discussed their opinions, but they listened to others speak.

The second question asked about gaps in the resources provided to perioperative team members following AEs. The group was made aware that some HCPs had peer support programs and others did not. Many were not aware that peer support programs were available for only certain HCPs. Many members discussed the need to bring the lack of support to their administrators' attention, since the Joint Commission advises members to advocate for themselves.

The third question pertained to the resources they would like to see available to perioperative team members following AEs. Many individuals in the group felt there should be a policy or protocol for HCP after an AE. The policy would ensure supportive interventions are provided following an AE to ensure that HCP's well-being is maintained.

The fourth question asked which measures the perioperative team can take to make sure members' needs are met following AEs. Many of the CRNAs felt that a policy should be implemented so that facilities could provide automatic support without the need to request it. The CRNAs believed that the inconsistency of support across organizations was a concern and should be addressed since AEs will and do occur.

The adequacy of the support resources or need for additional support resources was measured using the qualitative data collected through the SOAR analysis and the quantitative data collected from the SVEST survey. Survey responses were collected via the Qualtrics platform and provided a form of communication for HCPs and participants at the project facility. The participants indicated which form of support was adequate and desired after an AE.

The DNP project addressed three aims to assist in the development of recommendations for the project facility. Discussion of the three aims follows.

Aim A

The first aim was to determine the current support resources available to the perioperative team at the time of an AE. The seven SVEST dimensions and the two outcomes are presented in Table 3. Table 3 shows the percent of agreement, which indicates the level of inadequate support participants received, the mean score, standard deviation, Cronbach alpha, and scoring survey item representing the number of questions related to that dimension. The items that are related to the dimension in Table 3 are clearly outlined in Appendix D.

On the SVEST, nearly 50% of the perioperative participants reported distress after experiencing an AE. The majority reported psychological distress and 50% indicated they felt physical distress. The results indicated 66.7% of participants agreed that non-work-related support was most inadequate, 55.6% believed institutional support was inadequate, and 44.4% identified colleague and supervisor support as inadequate. The participants felt the most support after an AE was received from colleagues and supervisors. Half of the participants indicated the AE affected their professional self-efficacy. The two outcome dimensions indicated that, despite the provided resources, 50% of the perioperative providers believed turnover or absenteeism was an outcome after an AE.

The Cronbach alpha ranged from .157 for colleague support to .918 for absenteeism. Ideally, a reliable Cronbach alpha score is above .7, which demonstrates the validity of the dimensions assessed. Psychological distress, physical distress, supervisor support, professional self-efficacy, and absenteeism scores were valid. The colleague support, institutional support, non-work-related support, and turnover intention scores scored below .7, suggesting decreased validity. This may also have been due to the small sample size.

Table 3*Second Victim Experience Tool*

Dimension	Agreement: <i>N</i> (%)	Mean	SD	A	Items
Psychological Distress	8 (44.4)	3.097	0.777	.774	4
Physical Distress	9 (50.0)	2.778	.947	.846	4
Colleague Support	8 (44.4)	2.487	.572	.157	4
Supervisor Support	8 (44.4)	2.597	.713	.810	4
Institutional Support	10 (55.6)	2.741	.632	.526	3
Non-Work-Related Support	12 (66.7)	2.000	.767	.450	2
Professional Self-Efficacy	9 (50.0)	2.472	.742	.770	4
Turnover Intentions	9 (50.0)	1.806	.710	.428	2
Absenteeism	9 (50.0)	3.028	1.063	.918	2

Aim B

The second aim assessed the perioperative teams' experience with AEs. The data in Table 4 revealed correlations between demographics, dimensions, and outcomes. The SVEST data indicate there was a significant correlation between age, professional title, work experience, and institutional support. The results revealed that older registered nurses who had more experience were more likely to seek institutional support. There was a significant correlation between psychological distress and physical distress. Psychological distress was also significantly correlated with colleague support and professional self-efficacy. Participants who were suffering from psychological distress often received poor support from colleagues. Similarly, participants who experienced physical distress also received poor support from colleagues. Poor colleague and supervisor support correlated with low professional self-efficacy, which is consistent with the SOAR analysis. Poor supervisor support correlated with decreased

professional self-efficacy and the HCP's intention to turnover. Participants who reported decreased self-efficacy had an increased chance of the outcome of turnover.

Table 4*Correlations Between Demographic Characteristics and SVEST Dimensions*

Descriptors	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1. Age ^a	1												
2. Gender ^b	.381	1											
3. Title ^c	-.485*	.236	1										
4. Experience ^d	.792**	.313	-.153	1									
5. Psych Distress	-.170	-.221	.152	.174	1								
6. Physical Distress	.099	.085	.129	.310	.566*	1							
7. Colleague Support	-.049	.168	.194	.177	.541*	.653**	1						
8. Supervisor Support	-.079	.206	.118	-.017	.227	.355	.725**	1					
9. Institutional Support	-.615**	.149	.298	-.544*	.064	-.183	.220	.201	1				
10. Other Support	.132	.237	-.269	.035	-.111	-.334	.117	.027	.303	1			
11. Self-Efficacy	-.093	.136	.067	.002	.528*	.608**	.744**	.561*	.266	.323	1		
12. Turnover	-.091	.356	-.043	-.231	.036	.391	.446	.475*	.405	.378	.729**	1	
13. Absenteeism	.053	-.181	-.014	.011	.041	.240	.470	.287	-.047	-.270	-.018	.085	1

Note. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients are reported for associations between two continuous variables

Biserial correlations are reported for associations between binary and continuous variables

Phi correlations are reported for associations between two binary variables

^a 1 = 26-35, 2 = 36-45, 3 = 46-55, 4 = >55

^b 1 = Female, 2 = Male

^c 1 = Registered Nurse, 2 = Surgical Technician

^d 1 = < 5 years, 2 = 5-10 years, 3 = 11-19 years, 4 = 20-29 years, 5 = > 30 years

*p < .05 (2-tailed)

**p < .001 (2-tailed)

Aim C

The third aim was to identify the desired forms of support to mitigate distress after an AE, which are presented in Table 5. The results indicated that 83.3% desired a peaceful location to recompose, 72.2% desired immediate time away to recover, 66.7% wanted to discuss the AE with a trusted peer, and 55.6% wanted assistance from EAP or access to confidential assistance 24 hours a day. In terms of the least desired supportive intervention, 44.4 % did not want to have a discussion with a manager, supervisor or counselor. More than 60% of the participants wanted to discuss the AE with a respected peer, have a peaceful location to get away or a specific location to recover after the AE.

Table 5

Desired Forms of Support

Form of Support	Desired: <i>N</i> (%)	Not Desired: <i>N</i> (%)
The ability to immediately take time away from my unit for a little while	13 (72.2)	1 (5.6)
A specified peaceful location that is available to recover and recompose after one of these types of events	15 (83.3)	2 (11.1)
A respected peer to discuss the details of what happened	12 (66.7)	2 (11.1)
An employee assistance program that can provide free counseling to employees outside of work	10 (55.6)	1 (5.6)
A discussion with my manager or supervisor about the incident	8 (44.4)	4 (22.2)
The opportunity to schedule a time with a counselor at my hospital to discuss the event	8 (44.4)	4 (22.2)
A confidential way to get in touch with someone 24 hours a day to discuss how my experience may be affecting me	10 (55.6)	2 (11.1)

Discussion

The project collected both qualitative and quantitative data using the SVEST survey and SOAR analysis. Although the sample was small, the data provide rich detail regarding the participants' perceptions related to support after an AE. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the project was modified to adhere to social distancing restrictions. Perioperative providers identified supportive interventions they desired after an AE, as 70%. Eighty % of the participants wanted time to recover after the event, and 66% wanted to discuss the AE with a trusted peer.

The project's findings are consistent with the literature review with regards to peer support programs for SV. The current project facility has a S4USV program for physicians only. This program has been beneficial for the physicians because it provides reassurance that they have someone to talk to in confidence after an AE occurs. The literature indicates that the majority of HCPs believe that talking with a peer mitigates their distress after an AE (Gazoni et al., 2012). Based on the project's findings, a peer support program would benefit the participants. Peer support has proven to be most effective in addressing the needs of HCPs after an AE (Hu et al., 2012).

The results indicated that, despite providing support resources, there is much room for improvement. Perioperative team members were provided support from their colleagues and supervisor and less support from the institution or other non-work-related support after an AE. Even though the participants received support from colleagues and supervisors, the support was considered poor because it was associated with participants having increased turnover intention. This indicates the support received was not adequate.

According to the SVEST survey results, the current support resources are not sufficient because nearly half of the perioperative team members experienced distress after an AE. The participants experienced distress, and they are considering taking time off from work or leaving.

The participants identified colleagues and supervisors as their main source of support after an AE, but the majority agreed that institutional support services were inadequate. The data revealed that the support resources from the HCO are not sufficient to mitigate their stress following an AE. Support offered at the project facility included EAP, manager, supervisor or counselor. These support choices are the least desired by participants. The SVEST assessment brought to light the participants' needs following an AE. Although the organizations offer supportive interventions, these are not focused on the participants' specific needs and are inadequate to mitigate their distress.

The SVEST identified which support was important for the participants and what type of support was needed. The support resource requested by the majority of participants was time away to recover. This is currently not an option for the participants. The next support resource of most value was discussing the AE with a trusted peer. Discussion with the trusted peer depends on whom the participant trusts. The trusted peer may not be available, which may cause more distress. Lastly, the participants wanted 24-hour access to discuss the AE in confidence. This access is an option available through EAP, but participants seemed unaware of this fact.

The results from the focus group and SOAR analysis indicated that there is no protocol, policy or algorithm in place to assist CRNAs at their facility following an AE. Many of the CRNAs had not heard of the term SV before, but many had indicated that they have been in situations or heard of situations where a colleague was affected by an AE. The form of support the CRNAs desired varied from peer support, EAP, and a break to having a policy to ensure every member is afforded the same opportunity to mitigate their distress. Their discussion indicated a need for a policy to ensure their needs are met after an AE.

The participants' responses to the SVEST and the focus group helped to develop recommendations for supports. Healthcare organizations' leaders need to provide supportive

wellness resources beneficial for all HCP following AEs. Although HCO leaders do not want AEs to occur, the fact is that HCPs are experiencing them. The results indicated that there should be organized support to mitigate distress. Healthcare organizations' leaders need to protect the well-being of the HCP as they protect the well-being of their patients.

Limitations

There were three main limitations identified in the project. The SVEST survey was long. It took participants, on average, 13.4 minutes to complete. According to Qualtrics, there is a higher propensity for a participant to not complete a survey that is longer than 9 minutes (Vanette, 2021). This may have discouraged some participants from completing the survey. There were two unfinished surveys. In addition, the survey was sent to 64 individuals, and only 18 completed the survey, for a 28% response rate.

The project occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic, which required many changes to how it was implemented. Many participants were deployed daily to different units to support colleagues who were caring for COVID-19 positive patients with higher care needs, so potential participants were missed. The focus groups and SOAR data collection strategy were modified. These modifications resulted in including participants from different facilities and conducting a Zoom meeting. There were also modifications to the Iowa Model, implementing the SOAR analysis on Zoom, and not forming the team. In-person gatherings were prohibited.

Another limitation to the project was the requirement from the project facility's IRB, which did not allow the project author to assess colleagues on her own unit. The policy at the project facility indicated that the project author could not implement the project on her unit of work. However, this did not minimize the project's findings. The perspectives of nurses and surgical technicians provided valuable information regarding support after an AE.

Recommendations and Implications for Clinical Practice

The recommendations developed from this project target the need for support after an AE for the perioperative provider. The recommendations illustrated the need for individualized forms of support. Overall, the recommendations are not costly to implement and can be provided using existing resources or by developing a policy. These recommendations will be shared with management, leadership, and union leadership upon completion of this project. It is the goal of this project that the recommendations will be implemented to enhance the quality of care provided to SVs. Four recommendations were derived from the results.

First, after an AE, the HCP needs a break. To gather their thoughts, they need to take an immediate break. This will help to decrease the possibility of another AE occurring because the HCP was under stress. Second, HCO leadership should have a designated area where team members can go to gather their thoughts. This location could be in the perioperative area or another location in the hospital that provides a quiet and reflective area. Third, the HCO should expand the existing S4USV program to other HCPs. Through this expansion, the costs would be minimal since the S4USV program is established and integrated into the facility. This would address the need identified for a peer with whom to discuss the AE. Fourth, ongoing system improvement should focus on staff members' well-being.

Conclusion

Processes should be in place to address the needs of HCPs after an AE. The emotional well-being of all HCP who experience an AE should be addressed using a systematic approach. The lack of SV support is problematic for HCO leaders since the associated symptoms put the HCP at risk for further errors (Burlison et al., 2017). Since there are resources at the project facility for physicians, the same or similar support should be provided to other HCPs who will

experience the same emotions after an AE. When HCPs are supported, there is a decreased risk of being involved in a medical error (Burlison et al., 2017).

The SVEST survey and the SOAR analysis provided an opportunity for participants to voice their opinions regarding their perceptions of the HCO's level of support and the quality of that support following an AE. The key aspect of the survey and focus group was identifying the supportive interventions required. The literature review indicated that many HCOs do not assess the effectiveness of their resources or have a plan in place for HCP following an AE (Conway et al., 2011; van Pelt et al., 2019). It is necessary that HCO leaders engage their HCPs so that supportive interventions can be planned appropriately to mitigate distress after an AE. Our findings indicate that the forms of support HCPs need will be of minimal cost and of maximum gain. Overall, the project found a need to provide support to SV after an AE.

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Appendix A

Initial Search Strategy

Table A

Initial Search Strategy

Topic	Search Terms	Search Term Combinations	# found
Meaning of	Definition of Second Victim	Second Victim and Second Victim Phenomenon healthcare professionals	17
	Second Victim and physicians Second Victim and nurses Second Victims and Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist	Second Victims and Physicians Second Victim Phenomenon Second Victims and Second Victim Phenomenon Nurses Second Victim and CRNA	
Prevalence or incidence of Second Victim	Prevalence of Second Victim Phenomenon and Second Victim	Prevalence of	2
Emotional Impact	Impact of Second Victim Phenomenon	Impact of AEs, critical incidents and Second Victim	16
Outcomes	Outcome's burnout, absenteeism, intention to leave, substance abuse and suicide of second victim, Second Victim Phenomenon	Outcomes of Second Victim and nurses Outcomes of second victims and CRNAs Outcomes of Second Victims and healthcare professionals	16
Coping	Coping Mechanisms for second Victims and Second Victim Phenomenon	Coping mechanisms and nurses Coping mechanism and CRNA Coping and healthcare professionals	2
Screen for SV Survey and tools	Second Victims and Second Victim Phenomenon	Second Victims and healthcare professionals Second Victims and CRNA Second Victim and nurses	6
SVP Support	Second Victim phenomenon support SV and healthcare professionals	Support for healthcare professional's SV and CRNAs, nurses' perioperative team	5

Appendix B

Permission Letter

Southern California Permanente Medical Group

DATE: July 9, 2020

Kaiser Permanente Riverside Service Area Anesthesia and Peri-Operative Departments
10800 Magnolia Avenue
Riverside, Ca. 92505

To the Institutional Review Boards of Cal State University Fullerton and Kaiser Permanente:

We are writing this letter at the request of Laura Chavez to confirm that we are working with her as she commences her quality improvement project, "Second Victim Phenomenon: Quality Improvement Project in the Perioperative setting." We are aware that she will be conducting a staff survey and a focus group to conduct a Strengths, Opportunities, Aspiration and Results (SOAR) analysis at Kaiser Permanente Riverside Medical Center in the perioperative and anesthesia departments. Mrs. Laura Chavez will have the approval to do such procedures for as long as she has IRB approval to do so.

I also confirm that employees here at Kaiser Permanente Riverside Medical Center will be given the opportunity to participate in the recruitment or selection of participants. Staff in the perioperative and anesthesia units will have the ability to participate in the focus groups and complete the demographic and project Second Victim Experience Support Tool (SVEST) survey if they feel inclined to do so.

If any unanticipated problems or adverse events are to occur, it is up to Mrs. Laura Chavez to report these events to the IRB at Cal State University Fullerton and Kaiser Permanente and the Kaiser Permanente department administrator of anesthesia Renee Portillo and the operating room manager Jenny Schulte as promptly as possible.

Mrs. Laura Chavez's quality improvement project will be a valuable contribution to the improvement of our patients and the wellbeing of the perioperative and anesthesia department staff, and we will be happy to support this endeavor.

Sincerely,

*Alpha Soyjanhadi, RN, BSN
Assistant Department Administrator
Jenice Schulte RN BSN*

10800 Magnolia Avenue
Riverside, California 92505

Appendix C

Demographics

Demographics Questionnaire

How old are you?	Less than 25	26-35	36-45	46-55	Greater than 55
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What is your gender?	. Male	. Female	Other
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Professional title	CRNA	RN	Surgical technician	Anesthesia Technician
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Years of experience at this current profession?	. less than 5 years	5 to 10 years	11-19 years	20-29 years	greater than 30 years
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Appendix D

Second Victim Experience and Support TOOL (SVEST)

Instructions for participants:

“The following survey will evaluate your experiences with adverse patient safety events. These incidents may or may not have been due to error. They may also may oy may not include circumstances that resulted in patient harm or even reached the patient (near miss patient safety events). Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements that pertain to yourself and your own experience at this hospital” (Burlison et al., 2017, p. 9)

Survey item	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. I have experienced embarrassment from these instances.					
2. My involvement in these types of instances had made me fearful of future occurrences.					
3. My experience have made me feel miserable.					
4. I feel deep remorse for my past involvement in these types of events.					
5. The mental weight of my experience is exhausting.					
6. My experience with these occurrences can make it hard to sleep regularly.					
7. The stress from these situations has made me feel queasy and nauseous.					
8. Thinking about these situations can make it difficult to have an appetite.					
9. I appreciate my coworkers, attempts to console me, but their efforts can come at the wrong time.					
10. Discussing what happened with my colleagues provides me with a sense of relief.					
11. My colleagues can be indifferent to the impact these situations have had on me.					
12. My colleagues help me feel that I am still a good healthcare provider despite any mistakes I have made.					
13. I feel that my supervisor treats me appropriately after these occasions.					
14. My supervisors' responses are fair.					
15. My supervisor blames individuals.					
16. I feel that my supervisor evaluates these situations in a manner that considers the complexity of the patient care practices.					
17. My organization understands that those involved may need help to process and resolve any effects they may have on care providers.					
18. My organization offers a variety of resources to help me get over the effects of the involvement with these instances.					

19. The concept of concern for the well-being of those involved in these situations is not strong at my organization.

20. I look to close friends and family for emotional support after one of these situations happens.

21. The love from my closest friends and family helps me get over these occurrences.

22. Following my involvement I experienced feelings of inadequacy regarding my patient care abilities.

23. My experience makes me wonder if I am not really a good healthcare provider.

24. After my experience I became afraid to attempt difficult or high-risk procedures.

25. These situations do not make me question my professional abilities.

26. My experience with these events has led to take a position outside of patient care.

27. Sometimes the stress from being involved with these situations makes me want quit my job.

28. My experience with an adverse patient event or medical error has resulted in me taking a mental health day.

29. I have taken time off after one of these instances occur.

30. The ability to immediately take time away from my unit for a little while

31. A specified peaceful location that is available to recover and recompose after one of these types of events.

32. A respected peer to discuss the details of what happened.

33. An employee assistance program that can provide free counseling to employees outside of work.

34. A discussion with my manager or supervisor about the incident.

35. The opportunity to schedule a time with a counselor at my hospital to discuss the event.

36. A confidential way to get in touch with someone 24 hours a day to discuss how my experience may be affecting me.

Appendix E

Second Victim Experience and Support Survey (SVEST)

Scoring the survey responses

“To use the scores of this instrument to highlight opportunities for improvement, the following instructions for scoring the responses are provided. The first set of instructions is for the seven dimensions and two outcome variables. After converting the reverse-worded item responses (see survey below), compute mean scores for participants for each of the seven dimensions as well as the two outcome variables. The responses are rated on a 1–5 Likert scale, where higher scores represent greater amounts of second victim responses, the degree to which support resources are perceived as inadequate, and the extent of the 2 second victim–related negative work outcomes (i.e., turnover intentions and absenteeism). After computing mean scores for each participant, calculate the percentage and the number of the response means that represent agreement (i.e., the respondents who have a mean dimension and outcome score of 4.0 or higher). This scoring technique will provide results that are limited to the extent of negative effects of second victim experiences and opportunities to improve support resources” (Burlison et al., p. 101)

“For the items created to measure the desirability of support options, the following scoring instructions yield results based on which organizations can create and revise second victim resources. The responses for these items are rated on a 1–5 Likert scale, where a response of 4 or 5 represents the support option being desired and 1 or 2 represents support option being not desired. To capture the degree to which the support options are desired or not desired, calculate the percentage of desire responses (4 or 5) and not desired responses (1 or 2). Therefore, this scoring will yield the percentage desired and not desired for each support option, and these results can direct organizational support efforts” (Burlison et al., p. 101)

Survey Items

Psychological Distress

- I have experienced embarrassment from these instances.
- My involvement in these types of instances has made me fearful of future occurrences.
- My experiences have made me feel miserable.
- I feel deep remorse for my past involvements in these types of events.

Physical Distress

- The mental weight of my experience is exhausting.
- My experience with these occurrences can make it hard to sleep regularly.
- The stress from these situations has made me feel queasy or nauseous.
- Thinking about these situations can make it difficult to have an appetite.

Colleague Support

- I appreciate my coworkers' attempts to console me, but their efforts can come at the wrong time.
- Discussing what happened with my colleagues provides me with a sense of relief.
- My colleagues can be indifferent to the impact these situations have had on me.
- My colleagues help me feel that I am still a good healthcare provider despite any mistakes I have made.

Supervisor Support

- I feel that my supervisor treats me appropriately after these occasions.
- My supervisor's responses are fair.
- My supervisor blames individuals.
- I feel that my supervisor evaluates these situations in a manner that considers the complexity of patient care practices.

Institutional Support

- My organization understands that those involved may need help to process and resolve any effects they may have on care providers.
- My organization offers a variety of resources to help me get over the effects of involvement with these instances.
- The concept of concern for the well-being of those involved in these situations is not strong at my organization.

Non-Work-Related Support

- I look to close friends and family for emotional support after one of these situations happens.
- The love from my closest friends and family helps me get over these occurrences.

Professional Self-Efficacy

- Following my involvement, I experienced feelings of inadequacy regarding my patient care abilities.
- My experience makes me wonder if I am not really a good healthcare provider.
- After my experience, I became afraid to attempt difficult or high-risk procedures.
- These situations do not make me question my professional abilities.

Turnover Intentions

- My experience with these events has led to a desire to take a position outside of patient care.
- Sometimes the stress from being involved with these situations makes me want to quit my job.

Absenteeism

- My experience with an adverse patient event or medical error has resulted in me taking a mental health day.
- I have taken time off after one of these instances occurs.

Desired Forms of Support

- The ability to immediately take time away from my unit for a little while.
- A specified peaceful location that is available to recover and recompose after one of these types of events.
- A respected peer to discuss the details of what happened.
- An employee assistance program that can provide free counseling to employees outside of work.
- A discussion with my manager or supervisor about the incident.
- The opportunity to schedule a time with a counselor at my hospital to discuss the event.
- A confidential way to get in touch with someone 24 hours a day to discuss how my experience may be affecting me.

Appendix F

Dr. Scott's Approval

Hi Laura..... I enjoyed our phone conversation. It was great getting to know you! Attached please find some of the information that I promised as follows:

-Attachment #1 is the manuscript in which we introduced the SVEST tool. The tool is contained in the Appendix. The author team grants permission to individuals to use the tool with the request that whenever the findings are discussed (written or verbal) that you cite the original manuscript. There is no fee associated with using this tool. Please note that you will need to generate your instrument by using an electronic survey platform such as RedCap or Survey Monkey.

-Attachment #2 is the brochure that the forYOU Team provides during a peer conversation. I sent it to you in Word format so that you can make it your own. Feel free to adapt it as you see fit. My only ask is that appropriate attribution is given to the 'University of Missouri Health Care's forYOU Team.'

-Attachment #3 – okay, we didn't talk about this just in time resource for the peer supporters during our conversation, but I thought it might be a helpful resource for you. One side includes phone contacts, so the resource is handy. The opposite side identifies the components of our 4-step conversation guide. It helps give a bit more information for you.

-Attachment #4 is a flyer for our regional workshop. Unfortunately, I don't have the September flyer as of yet. I've asked for a new copy. Registration fees should be the same. Please contact them directly if you are interested and ask for the student discount. The date for the September workshop will be September 10th in St. Louis.

-Last but not least, I promised to connect you with another CRNA DNP student who is working on a similar project in her peri-operative area. I sent an introduction to Luci New via a separate email.

I think that covers everything that I promised. I wish you only the very best in your studies. Please keep me posted on your progress! You have chosen a rich topic that needs our attention..... thank you for caring for your co-workers!

Regards

Sue

Susan D. Scott, PhD, RN, CPPS, FAAN
Nurse Scientist/Adjunct Associate Professor
University of Missouri Health Care
Columbia, Missouri
scotts@health.missouri.edu
(573)882-5372

Appendix G

Iowa Model Revised

Note. This figure is adapted from Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa Model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidenced -Based Nursing* p.178. Copyright 2015.Reprinted with permission

Appendix H

Recruitment Flyer

Perioperative Teams' Experience with Adverse events

Prospective project: Needs Assessment

The purpose of this project is to: (A) assess current resources available to the perioperative team at the time of an adverse event, (B) assess the perioperative team's experience with adverse events, and (C) provide the project facility recommendations based on the perioperative team's needs for support after adverse events. We are conducting an electronic assessment on current available resources and needed resources. Your opinion matters and will be shared with management so that recommendations for support will be based off the perioperative team's needs.

Your participation is completely voluntary. "Your employment or performance evaluation at Kaiser Permanente or elsewhere is not affected whether you choose to join the study or not.

Where is electronic survey?

- The survey will be available in your kp email in box. It will take 10-15 minutes of your time. The survey will be available in the month of January and February

Who can participate?

- Peri-operative Registered Nurse
- Surgical Technician

If you're unsure if you meet the requirements, please call or email me:

- Michael Boytim EdD CRNA @ Michael.J.Boytim@kp.org or
- Laura Chavez CRNA
- Laura.Lbecerra@kp.org

Thank You For your
Time

Appendix I

Recruitment Email

Dear Potential Participant,

My name is Laura Chavez and I am a Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist at Kaiser Permanente in the Anesthesia Department. I am a staff member on a Prospective project being conducted by Dr. Boytim. The Prospective project focuses on the potential resources that are needed after an adverse event.

The aims of the Prospective project are as follows: Assess current resources available to the perioperative team at the time of an adverse event; assess perioperative teams' experience with adverse events and provide the project facility recommendations based on the perioperative team's need for support after adverse events. Your participation in this prospective project would require that you complete a short survey of 36 questions and demographic information, which will take approximately 10 to 20 minutes.

We assure you that your answers will be anonymous and your participation is voluntary. There is minimal risk associated with your involvement in the Prospective project. Your employment or performance evaluation at Kaiser Permanente or elsewhere will not be affected by your participation in the Prospective project.

If you have questions regarding this Prospective project, please contact Laura Chavez at Laura.l.Becerra@kp.org or Michael Boytim at Michael.J.Boytim@kp.org

Appendix J

Informational Sheet

KAISER FOUNDATION HOSPITALS

SOUTHERN CALIFORNIA PERMANENTE MEDICAL GROUP

Second Victim Phenomenon: Prospective
Project in the perioperative setting

Informational Sheet

INVESTIGATOR: Michael Boytim, EdD, CRNA
100 S. Los Robles #550
Pasadena, CA 91101

CO-INVESTIGATOR: Laura Chavez, CRNA
TELEPHONE: [REDACTED]

You are being asked to participate in a “Second Victim: Prospective Project in the perioperative setting” study, regarding your experience following an adverse event. The project involves an assessment of current resources and perioperative teams’ experiences with adverse events. This information will assist in understanding the need for additional resources after an adverse event.

Your decision to participate in this project is completely voluntary.

PURPOSE

The purpose of this project is to: (A) assess current resources available to the perioperative team at the time of an adverse event, (B) assess the perioperative team’s experience with adverse events, and (C) provide the project facility recommendations based on the perioperative team’s needs for support after adverse events.

DURATION

If you decide to participate, you will be asked to complete a survey of 36 questions that may take between 10- 20 minutes to complete. Additionally, we will ask you some basic demographic information such as your gender, length of work experience, and professional title.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

Your participation in the project is voluntary and will not affect your employment or performance evaluation at Kaiser Permanente. You can discontinue your participation at any time.

PROJECT PROCEDURE

As part of the project, you will be asked to complete an online survey. The survey link will be sent to your Kaiser Permanente email. The survey will take approximately 10-20 minutes to complete. The survey will not require that you identify yourself, it will be completely anonymous. Your responses will be used to determine the need for additional resources following adverse events. The deidentified information gathered from the project will be shared with management and leadership. The data will be used for educational purposes.

RISKS

There are minimal risks associated with participating in this quality improvement project. Some of the questions in the survey may trigger uncomfortable feelings or may cause you to reflect on an adverse event. Should you experience any discomfort while participating in the project you are free to withdraw for completing the survey.

BENEFITS

You may not directly benefit from participating in this study.

ALTERNATIVES

You do not have to participate in this study and your employment or performance evaluation at Kaiser Permanente will not be affected.

CONFIDENTIALITY

To maintain your confidentiality, your name will not be used nor connected in any manner to the survey you complete. The survey link will be sent to your email; however, the link is not tied to your email account. All data gathered from the surveys will be kept on a password protected computer in a locked and secured office at Kaiser Permanente Riverside Medical Center. Your email will not be included in the results of the project. Your email was only used as a method for sending the link to potential participants. All results will be in aggregate and no identifiable information will be attached to the dataset.

COMPENSATION

There is no compensation for your participation in the project.

COSTS

There are no costs associated with your participation in the project.

CONTACT INFORMATION

If you have any questions regarding this project, please contact Laura Chavez at laura.L.becerra@kp.org or Michael Boytim at michael.j.boytim@kp.org

If you have any questions regarding your rights as a project participant you may contact:

Armida Ayala, PhD, Director, Human Research Subjects Protection Office at (626) 405-3665 or Armida.Ayala@kp.org

Appendix K

CSUF IRB Approval

APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

November 3, 2020

**From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board**

To: PI: Laura Chavez

Application No. HSR-19-20-554

Study Title: Second Victim Phenomenon: Quality Improvement Project in The Peri-operative Setting

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(ii). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording).

Any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research would not reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, educational advancement, or reputation.

.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposed was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.**

Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project

title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Appendix L

Project Facility Approval

Institutional Review Board
Kaiser Permanente Southern California

December 11, 2020

KPSC Principal Investigator(s)

Michael Boytim, KPSC - Anesthesiology
100 S. Los Robles #550, Pasadena, CA 91101

KPSC Co-Investigator(s)

Laura Becerra

Non-KPSC Co-Investigator(s)

Study Title: SECOND VICTIM PHENOMENON: Prospective Quality Improvement Project in the perioperative setting (#12644)

On **12/11/2020**, a subcommittee of the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed and approved your new study.

In accordance with the requirements for research activities that present no more than minimal risk to subjects set forth in 45 CFR 46.110 the study referenced above qualified for expedited review under the following research category:

- Category 7: Research on individual or group characteristics or behavior (including, but not limited to, research on perception, cognition, motivation, identity, language, communication, cultural beliefs or practices, and social behavior) or research employing survey, interview, oral history, focus group, program evaluation, human factors evaluation, or quality assurance methodologies

Study Document(s):

Laura SVEST Informational Sheet Template kaiser with comments 12-1-2020
Qualtrics link 12-3-2020
Laura email script Kaiser 12-3-2020
Draft Flyer corrections 12-3-2020
SVEST Final kp 10-17-2020
LBecerra_nursing study review outcome to IRB (1) 10/19/2020

A subcommittee of the Institutional Review Board determined that this study satisfies the requirements of DHHS 45 CFR 46.204, research involving pregnant women and DHHS 45 CFR 46.404, research not involving greater than minimal risk.

In accordance with 45CFR 46.116, informed consent was waived by the IRB based on the following determination(s):

- The research involves no more than minimal risk to the subjects;
- The research could not practicably be carried out without the requested waiver or alteration;
- If the research involves using identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens, the research could not practicably be carried out without using such information or biospecimens in an identifiable format;
- The waiver or alteration will not adversely affect the rights and welfare of the subjects; and
- Whenever appropriate, the subjects or legally authorized representatives will be provided with additional pertinent information after participation.

The KPSC Principal Investigator (PI) is required to:

- Review the document entitled HIPAA Privacy Rule Instructions for Researchers available at http://irb.kp-scalresearch.org/5/HIPPA_Privacy_Rule_Instructions_for_Researchers.pdf
- Submit a complete final closure report of research activities.

And if applicable,

- Submit for IRB review, modifications to the study or any IRB-approved study document(s) before they are implemented **except** when necessary to eliminate apparent immediate hazards to one or more subjects. If you determine that an immediate modification is critical to eliminate hazards to one or more subjects, you must notify the IRB within five business days of having carried out such changes to your study.
- Submit Unanticipated Serious Adverse Event report(s) according to IRB policies and procedures and consistent with federal regulations.
- Submit Protocol Violation report(s) and other Unanticipated Problem Reports according to IRB policies and procedures and consistent with federal regulations

Sincerely,

Signature applied by Isabel M Sanchez on
12/14/2020 06:10:21 AM PST

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director
Human Research Subjects Protection Office
Institutional Review Board